

ARISTOTELNING NOTIQLIK SAN'ATIGA QO'SHGAN HISSASI

Mirzaquliyeva Oydinoy Shahobovna

Buxoro davlat pedagogika instituti

O'zbek tili va adabiyoti ta'lim yo'nalishi 3-O'TA-24 guruhi talabasi.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14953339>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Aristotelning notiqlik san'atiga qo'shgan hissasi hamda notiqlik nazariyasi, tamoyillari va kategoriyalari xususida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Aristotel, notiqlik, nutq, insoniyat tarixi, voizlik, muloqot shakllari.

Аннотация. В статье представлена информация о вкладе Аристотеля в искусство ораторского искусства, а также о теории, принципах и категориях ораторского искусства.

Ключевые слова: Аристотель, ораторское искусство, речь, история человечества, проповедь, формы общения.

Abstract. This article provides information about Aristotle's contribution to the art of oratory and the theory, principles, and categories of oratory.

Keywords: Aristotle, oratory, speech, human history, preaching, forms of communication.

Notiqlik san'ati qadim zamonlardan insonlarni o'ziga jalb qilgan san'atlardan biri hisoblanadi. Chiroyli nutq har doim muhim narsalar qatorida turadi. Insonlarning jamiyatda o'z o'rnini egallashda ham nutqning ahamiyati juda kattadir. Nutqi go'zal va ifodali bo'lgan, so'zlari manolarga boy bo'lgan shaxslarning nutqi har doim insonlarni o'ziga jalb qiladi va bunday shaxslar har doim e'zoz va e'tibor markazida bo'lishadi. Notiqlik san'ati o'z-o'zidan fan sifatidagi tarixi ham ancha qadimga borib taqaladi. Notiqlik san'ati asosan ritorika deb ishlatiladi. "Ritorika" grekcha so'z bo'lib, "notiqlik san'ati" degan ma'noni beradi.

Umumiy qilib aytganda ritorika notiqlik haqidagi fan hisoblanadi. Insoniyat tarixida o'zining tengsiz nutqlari, oratorligi bilan shuhrat qozongan shaxslar bisyor. Ulardan biri, aynan shu fanning asoschisi sifatida ko'riladigan Aristoteldir. Aristotel buyuk yunon faylasuflaridan biri, u ta'bir joiz bo'lsa jamiki allomalarning ustozlari hisoblanadi. U miloddan avvalgi 384-yilda Egey dengizi yoqasidagi Stagir shaharchasida tug'ilgan.

Keyinchalik Makedoniya ta'siriga tushgan bu shaharcha dastlab Ellada ittifoqi doirasida bo'lgan, u shahar-davlat hisoblangan, makedoniya ta'siriga tushmasdan oldin mustaqil holda Ellada ittifoqidan ajrab chiqqan. Stagir shaharchasida tug'ilgani tufayli Aristotelni ba'zida Stagiriy deb ham atashadi, biroq bu juda kam manbalarda tilga olinadi.

Aristotelning otasi makedoniyaning qirollik oilasi bilan yaqin aloqada bo'lgan. O'z-o'zidan Aristotel makedoniya shohi Iskandarga murabbiylik qilgan.

Keyinchalik deyarli barcha fanlarga o'z hissasini qo'shgan Aristotel dastlab tabiblikni o'rgangan. Chunki uning otasi mashhur tabiblar sulolasidan edi. O'smirlik chog'ida otasidan yetim qolgan aristotel tabiblik faoliyatini shu yerda tomahalliy hokim bolalariga saboq beradi va shu yerda bilimlarini chuqurlashtiradi, asosiy e'tiborini falsafaga qaratadi, keyingi dunyoqarashining tamal toshlari mana shu davrda qo'yiladi. Keyinchalik u Filip II tomonidan saroyga taklif qilinadi, Filip II Aristotelni o'g'li Iskandarga murabbiy etib tayinlaydi.

Bu tarixdagi eng muhim voqealardan biri hisoblanadi. Iskandarning jahon tarixidagi eng buyuk sarkardalardan biri bo'lib yetishishiga aynan Aristotelning ta'lim-tarbiyasi sabab bo'lgan, u iskandarni dostonlardagi kabi qahramonona ruhda tarbiyalagan. Jumladan, Iskandarning quyidagi gapi ham buning to'g'riligini isbotlaydi: "Men Aristotelni otamday hurmat qilaman, chunki otam menga hayot berdi, ustozim esa menga hayotni o'rgatdi". Otasining do'stlari uning qiziqishlaridan kelib chiqib Aristotelni ilm-fanga yo'naltirishgan. Shu sababli aristotel Afinadagi ma'lum-u mashhur Platon akademiyasiga o'qishga kirgan. Aristotel bu yerda naqt o'n ikki yil tahsil oladi va keyin o'zi shu yerda ta'lim ham beradi. Aristotel Platonning sevimli shogirdi edi.

Platon vafot etib, akademiya nomaqbul kishi qo'lga o'tgach Aristotel Afinani tark etadi.

Aristotel Assos shahrida mahalliy hokim bolalariga saboq beradi va shu yerda bilimlarini chuqurlashtiradi, asosiy e'tiborini falsafaga qaratadi, keyingi dunyoqarashining tamal toshlari mana shu davrda qo'yiladi. Keyinchalik u Filip II tomonidan saroyga taklif qilinadi, Filip II aristotelni o'g'li Iskandarga murabbiy etib tayinlaydi.

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Aristotelning bir necha yuzlab asarlar yozgani taxmin qilinadi. U o'zidan juda boy falsafiy meros qoldirgan. Shular sirasiga kiruvchi "Ritorika" notiqlik san'atining muhim manbalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Aristotel bu asarida bir qator masalalarni ko'rib chiqadi. Jumladan, ritorikaning foydasi, maqsadi va asoslari; ritorikaning dialektikaga munosabati, sillogizm bilan antimemaning o'zaro munosabati, notiqlik san'atining barcha fanlar uchun umumiyligi; nima uchun tadqiqotchilar ko'pincha sudlov nutqlari haqida gapirishni ma'qul ko'rishlari; notiqlik san'ati sistemasini tuzish mumkin yoki yo'qligi; sudya hal etishi kerak bo'lgan masalalar; avvalgi notiqlik

san'ati sistemalarining qoniqarli emasligi; qonun nega barcha muammolarni o'zi hal etishi kerakligi va buning sabablari; notiq nimalarni isbotlamog'i kerakligi va hokazolar. "Ritorika" asari ritorikaning dialektika bilan umumiy va o'xshash tomonlarining muhokmasi bilan boshlanadi.

Dialektika grekcha so'z bo'lib, diaolog, suhbat ma'nosini beradi. Platon uni shunday ta'riflaydi: "Dialektik – savol berib, ro'g'ri javob izlovchi odam. Dialektika san'ati – dehqon dalaga urug' sepganday, donishmand ko'ngillarga urug' sepadi, ulardan haqiqat unib chiqadi va bu hosil abadiy, o'lmas boylikdir". Notiqlik nega aynan san'at deyiladi? Buning boisi qadimgi davrlardayoq notiqlik san'at darajasigacha ko'tarilgan.

Uni san'atday e'zozlashgan. Maxsus maktablarda mana shu san'at o'rgatilgan. Notiqlik san'ati juda ko'p o'rinda asqotadi. Misol uchun, omma oldida chiqish, rasmiy chiqish, auditoriya oldida chiqish, axborot yetkazish, rasmiy odob, ko'ngilochar yig'inlardagi nutq kabilar misol bo'la oladi. Notiqlik hamma sohada birday muhim san'atlardan biri hisoblanadi. Meditsina sohasida ham go'zal nutqning o'rni beqiyosdir. Ba'zida tuzalmas dardga muhtalo bo'lgan bemorlar ham bittagina shirin so'z va e'tibor bilan ular yana sog'lom hayotlariga qaytishadi. Bu ham nuqning qudrati bilan bo'ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, nutq—qalblarida zabt etuvchi sehr tafakkurni yurituvchi nur.

So'z bilan yurakni yayratish ham, ado qilish ham mumkin. Shunday ekan har bir so'zlayotgan nutqimizga e'tiborli bo'laylik!

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